

Speculation on the Photon Momentum and Electric Field Part 2

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. March 19, 2026

In Part 1, we argued that it is no coincidence that the photon free particle wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, which we call a complex probability that conserves energy and momentum, has a real part which matches the electric field of a photon. In particular, we argued that even if one did not know Maxwell's electromagnetic laws, one would postulate a force linked to a photon which behaved as $\cos(-Et+px)$.

Here, we reexamine Maxwell's electromagnetic equations. These are presumably deterministic differential equations and the photon solution with perpendicular electric and magnetic fields in a plane perpendicular to motion with each field changing as $\cos(-Et+px)$ for motion in the x direction, a seemingly deterministic solution. This deterministic solution, however, seems to be problematic for the following reason. If one considers one-dimensional reflection-refraction according to the prescription of (1), one writes a continuity equation for the electric field of an incoming photon with a reflected and refracted one, and another continuity equation for the first derivative. Physically, this appears to be a steady stream approach as well as a mathematical continuity one. The solution in (1) is obtained without any notion of probability until the last line: $1 = \text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Probability}(\text{refract})$. The situation, however, is completely probabilistic from the beginning we argue and so one should understand how a deterministic electric (and magnetic field) is actually associated with probability. (Furthermore, photon interference and diffraction are also probabilistic.)

We have argued in previous notes that examination of special relativity, in particular, the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px = \text{constant}(x,t)$, leads to a probability for interaction of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ for both a particle with rest mass and a photon. This probability conserves E,p, but at first glance does display the inherent force in the problem. It is the inherent force which delivers E,p. Probabilistically, there is an uncertainty associated with the interaction time of \hbar/E and with interaction position, \hbar/p . These should be associated with the inherent force. As a result, the photon electric field, which acts as a force, cannot be precisely as described by $\cos(-Et+px)$ because this violates the notion of \hbar/p and \hbar/E . Rather, this formula is an expression of probability of the action of the force. One ultimately does not have a deterministic situation, we argue.

In Part 1, we noted that a rest mass m_0 is associated with a force (inertia) as well as energy and momentum, which are proportional to m_0 . A photon has E and p and so should be associated with a force as it may render its energy to an object. The interesting thing about the photon is that it has no rest frame, even for the force. Given that $\exp(-im_0 c t)$ describes the probability associated with a rest force m_0 , we suggest that for a force linked with a moving photon, one should consider $\cos(-Et+px)$. This was already proposed in Part 1. This means that instead of considering the momentum as delivering the force, as it is proportional to m_0 for a particle with rest mass, for a photon, the electric field represents probabilistic force rendering, even though it is real and appears to be deterministic. Given that the electric field (inherent force) changes as $\cos(-Et+px)$, one may see that this force may change sign, but momentum must be in one direction. This suggests the presence of a second vector, together with the electric field in a quadratic arrangement with both becoming negative at the same time, i.e. both

following $\cos(-Et+px)$. One may then create energy and momentum using $\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E}$ and $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ for momentum. In such a case, energy and momentum would be cycle averages as the electric field changes as $\cos(-Et+px)$.

The Central Notion of Inherent Force in Quantum Mechanics

Given that a free particle wavefunction (we suggest it is a complex probability) is:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \text{ a Lorentz invariant ((1))}$$

One might think that energy E and p are the central variables of consequence, together with $x=vt$ for a particle with rest mass and $x=ct$ for a photon. We have argued in previous notes, however, that an inherent force is the central variable of consequence. For a particle with rest mass, we argue that inertia, proportional to m_0 , is the inherent force. In this case, momentum and energy, conserved quantities, happen to be proportional to m_0 . Given that E and p are conserved, ((1)) is a probability which demonstrates/enforces conservation of these quantities. For a particle with rest mass, however, it is known that $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ and so p and E are linked with a force. We have suggested in previous notes that a photon also must be linked with a force for energy and momentum to have meaning. We called the force the electric field (and the magnetic field also creates force). We argued that the different inherent forces accounted for the differences in spin. In Part 1, we suggested that even though ((1)) is linked with E and p conservation, it should also be linked to force and we postulated that

$$\text{Electric field} = e_j \cos(-Et+px) \text{ for motion in } x \text{ with the field along } y \text{ ((2))}$$

must be consistent with ((1)). Here we wish to consider this idea in more detail.

Deterministic Theory of a Photon

The main purpose of this note is to contrast the probabilistic nature of photons in the 2-slit interference experiment and one dimensional reflection-refraction problem with the deterministic theory of photons which follows from Maxwell's electromagnetic equations. Maxwell's equations are deterministic differential equations for the electric and magnetic fields which include charge and current sources. If one sets the charges and currents to zero, one obtains classical wave equations separately for the electric and magnetic fields with a speed of $1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0} = c$, the speed of light in a vacuum. Thus, the electric and magnetic fields behave as:

$$\cos(-Et+px) \text{ where } x \text{ is the direction of motion and the } E \text{ and } B \text{ fields lie in a } z\text{-}y \text{ plane ((3))}$$

Furthermore, one may create a continuity equation:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } (.5\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}) + 1/\mu_0 \text{ grad dot } (\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}) = 0 \text{ for a photon ((4))}$$

EI=electric field, B=magnetic field

((3)) and ((4)) appear to be deterministic expressions. The term $.5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B$ is energy density and $1/\mu_0 E \times B$, momentum density. One averages over a period to find the E and p values. Given the deterministic theory of Maxwell and the deterministic result of the photon ((4)), the question we ask is: How does probability arise?

We note that (1) describes one dimensional reflection-refraction strictly in a steady state continuity approach. In particular, an incident photon may reflect or refract (probabilistic situation), but mathematically (in (1)), one ensures continuity of the electric field and its first derivative. There is really no notion of probability in this approach until the last line. In particular, one writes:

$$A \cos(-Et+px) + B \cos(-Et-px) = C \cos(-Et+ p_1 x) \quad \text{at } t=0, x=0 \quad ((5a))$$

$$Ap \cos(-Et+px) - p B \cos(-Et-px) = Cp_1 \cos(-Et+ p_1 x) \quad \text{at } t=0, x=0 \quad ((5b))$$

This allows one to find expressions for B/A and C/A, the reflected and refracted fluxes divided by the incident flux. Then, finally, the probabilistic statement is

$$AA/c = BB/c + CC/c_1 \quad ((6))$$

The point we wish to make is that ((6)) is a strictly probabilistic statement, but nowhere does one see probability theory arise in the computation of (1). One simply uses continuity. We wish to have a specific probabilistic theory from step one in order to try to interpret ((4)) in a probabilistic manner. This is the approach taken in Part 1, which we try to develop further here.

The Case for Probability and the Notion of Inherent Force

We suggest that the notion of an inherent force associated with a particle is the key underlying idea. If a particle (with rest mass or photon) has an inherent force, it may be also associated somehow with energy and momentum which are linked to two ideas:

((7a)) Energy and Momentum are conserved

((7b)) Energy and Momentum are linked to special relativity

As a result, we argue that is easy to consider the free particle wavefunction (which we call a complex probability)

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((8))$$

as strictly a statement about E,p. We suggest that one must identify an inherent force and that it is this inherent force which describes the difference in spin for a particle with rest mass versus a photon, even though ((8)) holds for both.

In the case of a particle with rest mass, we argue that m_0 (inertia) is the inherent force. Thus, m_0 represents a force as well as being proportional to energy and momentum. In order to measure the inertial force, one must push m_0 until it receives a tiny velocity v , i.e. an energy and momentum. Thus, inertia, energy and momentum are intertwined. For a particle with rest mass, p is proportional to the inertial force and so $\exp(ipx)$ represents a complex probability linked to different positions at which the inertial force (enhanced by v) can strike. We note that ((8)) ensures conservation of energy and momentum for products of probabilities.

The situation for a photon seems to be more complicated, but we have argued in previous notes that the electric field (and its associated B magnetic field) are the inherent forces. We have shown that this approach (i.e. finding a differential equation linear in the inherent force and linked to p, E) yields the correct spin $\frac{1}{2}$ and spin 1 descriptions. Given that a photon is linked with an inherent force, this force should be linked with a transfer of energy and momentum. Unfortunately, energy and momentum in the photon case are not proportional to the inherent force which is a vector. In the case of a particle with a rest mass, one has a number or rotational scalar. This means that the force associated with inertia can be in any direction and that one may have a rest frame. A photon moves at a speed of c and so one cannot push on it to create speed. We argue that this is the reason that it does not have an inertia or inherent force as a number, but must have a vector force. Two issues then arise:

Is the photon's inherent electric field a constant? ((9a))

How is the electric field, a vector, linked to momentum and energy? ((9b))

If the photon has an inherent force (electric field), this force can do work and transfer energy from the photon to an object with which it interacts. If an inherent force exists, an energy and momentum must exist and these must be conserved and linked to special relativity.

If a photon can only move at the speed of c , then the inherent force (electric field) must move with it. At the same time, it seems that it is the electric which does not arise from a source (like a rest mass source or charge source), but actually defines the particle. As a result, the electric field is probably not a constant moving in space, but rather a function of x, t . It must also be linked to E and p in a Lorentz invariant manner. This suggests that it should be a function of:

$$-Et + px \quad ((10))$$

At this point, no notion of probability has been discussed. We have argued in previous notes, however, that a probabilistic theory emerges from ((10)), if this is viewed as a kind of potential. In particular, if $-Et + px$ has a value at x, t , the same value holds for:

$$x + \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad t + \hbar/E \quad ((11))$$

We suggest that ((11)) means that one has a probabilistic theory because one does not know if the inherent force acts at x, t or ((11)), or somewhere in between. We argue that $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ pertains to the probabilistic nature of the inherent force and not momentum, as argued in Part 1. In the case of a particle with rest mass, the inherent force is proportional to p , but in the photon

case, this seems to be a problem. If $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ must be linked to the inherent force and the electric field must be real, we argued in Part 1, that one must have:

Electric field proportional to $\cos(-Et+px)$ ((12))

The electric field, however, changes direction and so cannot represent momentum, which must be in a fixed direction. This suggests a second force (or force like vector) which also changes like ((12)). Then, one may create a rotational scalar and vector using:

$E \cdot E$ and $B \cdot B$ for rotational scalars and $E \times B$ for a vector if B goes as $\cos(-Et+px)$ as well ((13))

We suggest that even if one did not have Maxwell's electromagnetic equations, one could reach these conclusions.

Link with Deterministic Photon Solution

We noted in an above section that Maxwell's em equations are considered to be deterministic (even though some people in the literature consider them to be probabilistic) as is the solution for the electric field $\cos(-Et+px) e_j$ where e_j is a unit vector in the y direction and the photon moves in the x direction. Given that a probabilistic theory, which follows from $-Et+px$, exists, there is uncertainty in the inherent force hit based on $\hbar/E = \Delta t$ and $\hbar/p = \Delta x$. Thus, one cannot consider $\cos(-Et+px)$ for the electric field to be deterministic. Rather, even though it is a real function, it is associated with a probability for the electric field to hit within \hbar/p and \hbar/E . One may see that $E \cdot E$ and $B \cdot B$ become 0 for certain x, t combinations, but we argue that this should be considered in terms of a probability for the forces to strike. As a result, $E \times B$ as momentum density is a somewhat unusual quantity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that it is inconsistent with experiment (two slit interference and one dimensional reflection-refraction) to consider a photon as a deterministic object with $E = \text{constant} * \cos(-Et+px) e_j$ and $B = \cos(-Et+px) e_k$ for motion along x. The fields E, B create the photon and so have to be associated with a motion of c as well as creating E and p . The fact that they oscillate is linked to the probabilistic nature of both a particle with rest mass and a photon and follows from $-Et+px$ have x, t and $x+\hbar/p, t+\hbar/E$ as solutions with the same value. This leads to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ as a probability which conserves E, p , but also describes the inherent force of a particle. For a particle with rest mass, this force is m_0 (inertia), but for a photon it is the electric field (with the associated B). We argue that one cannot consider electric field = constant * $\cos(-Et+px)$ as deterministic. Rather it is the inherent force (both for a particle with rest mass and a photon) which is associated with probability. In other words, the inherent force is associated with probabilistic, and not deterministic strikes. Given that a force can render energy, E and p must be associated with a particle/photon and E, p must be conserved and

follow special relativity. This places constraints on the probability linked with the inherent force, i.e. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change